

THE ROLE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CRITICAL THINKING

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6945598>

Abdunabiyeva Maftunakhan Solijan

Andijan State Pedagogical Institute

Master's student of information technology in education

Kasimjonova Hamidakhan Botirjon

Student of the Faculty of Physics and Mathematics of Andijan State University

Abstract: *This article describes feedback on the development of students' critical (analytical) thinking, their importance, and their theoretical basis. In addition, the main principles that the teacher should follow during the educational process and the problems of developing students' creative abilities were discussed.*

Key words: *interactive methods, critical thoughts, creative possibilities, didactic games, logical thinking, traditional methodology, exchange of ideas.*

Critical thinking is based on the ability to express one's opinion on a given issue or problem, to critically re-perceive the opinions of others, to justify and maintain one's point of view. To further clarify this rule, thinking is a process similar to reading, writing, speaking, and hearing. It is an active, co-ordinating process that includes the idea of a reality.

Critical (analytical) thought is important because:

- helps to understand the meaning of complex variability of life;
- encourages the open mind of the team;
- means communication, mutual understanding and respect;
- creating conditions for personal development, etc.

Grounding of critical (analytical) thinking in the educational process:

1. Cultivates mutual respect between teacher (pedagogue) and pupil-student and between pupil-student and pupil-student.
2. The student's own experience is used during the training.
3. The specific educational content is used in a clear and appropriate manner according to the requirements of the student.
4. Educational materials are used in problem solving.
5. Different opinions and views are integrated.
6. Initial conditions are accepted and checked.

7. Education is given through the relationship between the teacher (pedagogue) and the students or between the students themselves.

8. Conditions are created for independent education of students and methods are chosen according to their level of preparation.

The didactic game technologies used in the course of the training are aimed at activating the cognitive activity of the student, independent work on textbooks and additional literature, developing the culture of speech and communication, consciously directing them to the profession. Getting the goal right in overcoming difficulties, analyzing various situations, prepares the ground for making the right conclusions [1].

The organization of problematic or controversial training in accordance with the requirements of educational programs is important in the development of critical and analytical thinking. In the educational process, two types of discussion classes are used: scientific discussion classes and free thinking classes.

Interactive methods are a set of actions aimed at mutual exchange of ideas, filling of mutual ideas, sometimes non-verbal, sometimes verbal influence [2]. In the application of the interactive method, intellectual activities based on interaction are not limited to performing the function of influence or motivation, and guiding the subjects of cooperation to creative research, helping to open (discover) an unknown situation. can also perform functions of creating mental reasoning.

In mastering the educational content, the following interactive methods are used in accordance with the students' level of knowledge, level of mastery, source of education, didactic tasks:

- demonstration method of teaching;
- method of independent work;
- problem-heuristic modeling method;
- scientific research methods;
- problem-research and reproductive methods of teaching;
- inductive and deductive methods of teaching;
- control and self-control methods of teaching.

Methods include the following groups:

Methods of the first group: methods of hearing educational information (oral methods: story, lecture, conversation, etc.).

Methods of the second group: methods of visual transmission and reception of educational information (visual method, visual presentation, etc.).

The third group of methods: providing educational information through practical labor activities (practical methods, exercises, laboratory work, creating programs, solving problems and test tasks, labor activities, etc.).

Various strategies are used in lesson systems based on interactive methods. In this case, students are not prohibited from using covert methods (book, notes, etc.), on the contrary, the use of such methods is encouraged.

To develop students' creative abilities, encourage them to make non-standard solutions along with ready-made standard solutions in solving problems, bring out their inner feelings, encourage them to think logically, teach them to compare, teach them to think privately, their intellectual. the problem method is used in order to form intellectual qualities and develop them at a higher level in a certain direction.

How is a problematic situation created? For this, a task to be completed will be announced. Now, in order to perform this task, the student remembers the knowledge and skills he has, while realizing the lack of knowledge he has acquired so far, a certain psychological conflict occurs in the student's personality. The problem in Gal is to find new knowledge, talents and skills to complete the task and to complete this task. This situation is the starting process of problematic education.

The pedagogue smartly manages the process of students' independent performance of the task, carefully observes it, and if necessary calls for live communication. During the students' logical thinking, their live observation, the frame of mind is consistently taken into account by the pedagogue, and at the end of the study, he announces the points or grades assigned to the active students. This method is used in order to form generalized psychological and methodological knowledge, talents and skills of students, to further strengthen their experiences from a critical point of view, to test them in the conditions of real practice, and to further enrich practical skills with new knowledge.

It is known that the content of any subject is selected according to the purpose set for teaching. Appropriate methods are chosen for its mastery. Then the teaching tools and, finally, the form of teaching are selected accordingly.

Appropriate content and methods are selected for each educational stage depending on the students' psychological preparation and level of thinking or assimilation of acquired knowledge. Each stage has its own content logic and methods. In education, there is always a problem of content and methods, these problems are inextricably linked[3]. Problems in educational methods "How do we teach whom?" related to the question, and it follows that the development of

educational methods depends on its content. These two problems are in opposition to each other and complement each other.

The purpose of the methodology is to create a new educational subject (subject) from this subject and to ensure the mastery of this subject. Such educational subjects should satisfy all the demands and needs of the student, be based on the principle of "reading first, then teach to teach this reading" based on the requirements of modern pedagogical technologies, the student's mastery of the educational material. It is necessary to take into account the characteristics of indicators and mastery levels, setting control tasks based on the "simple-to-complex" rule in acquiring theoretical and practical knowledge, and individual and differentiated approaches to students.

In the traditional method, taking into account the development of the student's personality, his knowledge becomes a skill. and it is clear that no importance is attached to the development of it until the qualification. The teacher tries to give the student as much information as possible about the subject being studied. The teacher does not always adhere to the three-stage model of knowledge: gathering information, selecting and processing information, and applying learned information. Next, the student's cognitive activity (acquired knowledge) should raise him to a new level of cognitive activity, that is, to the process of activation of this cognitive activity. Only then will knowledge become skills, and skills become skills [4]. The activation of students' cognitive activity is based on a number of principles: interest in learning science, based on basic expressions, use of problem methods, organization of independent work, organization of collective and individual work, use of visual and technical tools, connection of educational content with life. In short, establishment of interdisciplinarity, etc. From this, the main principles that the teacher must follow in the educational process are derived:

- instilling in the student a sense of self-confidence;
- providing the student with the necessary help in a timely manner.

In order to find out the critical opinion of students about subjects, the following leaflets were distributed:

1. I listened to the lecture and wrote it down, but I did not fully understand the essence of the material being mastered in one period.
2. The content and form of higher education is somewhat different from that of secondary school.
3. I feel difficulty in using scientific concepts, terms and definitions.
4. I can't understand the essence of lectures and seminars.

5. There are some discrepancies between theoretical knowledge and practice.
6. There is a lack of reasonable methods of planning independent activities.
7. There is very little time left for independent education.
8. During the academic year, some materials are collected for individual work.
9. I cannot concentrate due to lack of emotional stability during rating control.
10. Absence of primary sources for workshop training and preparation for rating control will lead to poor outcomes.

Developing critical thinking is not an easy task. It is not a task that is completed and forgotten at a certain age. At the same time, there is no one-size-fits-all path to critical thinking. But there is a set of specific educational conditions that help the formation of critical thinking.

It is necessary to give students time and opportunity to acquire the experience of critical thinking, that is;

- to give students an opportunity to think;
- acceptance of various ideas and opinions;
- ensuring students' activity in the educational process;
- to instill confidence in each student's ability to think critically;
- it is necessary to appreciate the occurrence of critical thinking.

In this regard, students:

- gaining self-confidence, understanding the value of one's own thoughts and ideas;
- active participation in the educational process;
- listening attentively to different opinions and ideas;
- he should be ready to form his own judgments and return from them.

Critical (analytical) thinking is directly related to student activity. Because students are slow listeners, they have the belief that the teacher is knowledgeable or that the text reflects his knowledge, and because of this, the teacher is responsible for their knowledge. Active participation of students in the educational process and willingness to take responsibility for their own learning gives expected results in critical reflection. Pedagogical approach of encouraging students to think, to share their ideas and opinions with each other increases their activity.

During the organization of the thinking process, it is necessary to instill in the minds of students that their opinions and the results of their critical analysis are valuable. When the teacher (pedagogue) requires students to simply process certain material, he should be free from ready-made templates and templates [5]. This leads students to believe that mechanically reproducing the ideas of others is most important and valuable. In fact, students need to be able to show that their

own opinions, ideas and visions are valuable. Students themselves need to be able to believe that their opinions are valuable and that they are considered to be a very important and important contribution to the discussion process.

The reflection process involves students exchanging ideas with each other. In the exchange of ideas, students are also required to listen carefully, to refrain from imposing their own point of view on the interrogator, and from correcting the opinions of other speakers. In return, students will have the opportunity to use the collective opinions of others. As a result of a wide-ranging discussion, students become more able to analyze and define their own ideas, and to draw on a system of ideas that they have created in their knowledge and life experiences. In organizing the thinking process, there are several models of conducting it, that is, self-confidence, active participation in work, sharing ideas with peers and the teacher, being able to listen to the opinions of others, etc.

In conclusion, it can be said that the development of critical (analytical) thinking of students in the educational process of higher educational institutions, and the implementation of educational principles play an important role in the self-management of students.

REFERENCES:

1. Tolipov O'.Q, Usmonboyeva M. Practical foundations of pedagogical technologies (Textbook) Tashkent. OzRFA "Fan" publishing house 2006.
2. Saidahmedov N. New pedagogical technologies (theory and practice). - Tashkent: Finance publishing house 2003.
3. Faberman B.L., Musina R.G., Jumaboyeva F.A. Modern methods of teaching in higher educational institutions. T.: 2003.
4. Azizkhojaeva N. N. Pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills. – Tashkent: TDPU, 2003.
5. Tolipova J., Numonova N. Modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process. / "People's education" magazine, 2002.